

INSTITUTIONAL HEALTH CHECK: AN INTEGRATED ANALYSIS OF LEADERSHIP STRENGTHS, ETHICAL ISSUES, AND ORGANIZATIONAL IMPROVEMENT AREAS IN A PHILIPPINE LOCAL COLLEGE

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ABSTRACT

Institutional health assessments offer systematic evidence on leadership practices, ethical standards, and organizational dynamics in higher education. This study conducted an institutional health check to evaluate leadership strengths, ethical issues, negative workplace behaviors, and recommend improvements within a local higher education institution. A descriptive qualitative approach was used, employing an open-ended leadership evaluation tool administered to all faculty and staff. A total of 232 responses were analyzed thematically, guided by Braun and Clarke's six-phase framework. The findings identified four key leadership strengths: effective communication characterized by clarity and responsiveness; strategic, mission-aligned planning; empowerment through appropriate delegation and guidance; and professionalism demonstrated by fairness and integrity. Ethical concerns and workplace issues were also reported, including inconsistencies in accountability, perceived favoritism in decision-making, lapses in professional conduct, procedural irregularities, communication tone issues, and concerns about attendance, task alignment, and interpersonal sensitivity. Participants suggested improvements, including clearer communication protocols, more

consistent decision-making, greater leadership accountability, enhanced team collaboration, systematic tracking and documentation, and expanded professional development opportunities. The results supported the development of a corrective action framework that links diagnostic insights to recommended interventions across training, policy updates, and mentorship. This study provides evidence to support organizational strength, demonstrating the value of institutional health checks as diagnostic tools for enhancing leadership capacity, ethical culture, and operational processes in higher education.

Keywords: *Institutional health assessment, leadership practices, ethical concerns, organizational behavior, higher education governance, continuous quality improvement.*

INTRODUCTION

Academic excellence, coupled with organizational integrity, ethical governance, and a culture of continuous improvement, is increasingly anticipated by Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Accreditation bodies such as the Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges, and Universities (PAASCU), as well as regulatory agencies such as the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), emphasize leadership accountability, ethical practices, and institutional responsiveness as key indicators of quality. In this regard, regular institutional self-assessments serve as a valuable mechanism for diagnosing organizational health and guiding evidence-based decision-making reforms.

Institutional health checks, systematic reviews of leadership practices, ethical culture, and workplace dynamics, are widely recognized as diagnostic tools that help HEIs identify strengths and areas for improvement. These assessments go beyond compliance with accreditation requirements; they establish a baseline for strategic planning and organizational development. Research highlights that effective leadership and transparent governance are strongly linked to organizational trust and institutional performance (Nguyen et al., 2017). Conversely, ethical lapses and ongoing negative workplace behaviors weaken collaboration and stakeholder confidence.

A newly established local higher education institution faces increasing demands related to organizational health, capacity building, and regulatory compliance as it expands. As a local government-funded institution, it faces challenges in developing systems, enhancing leadership structures, and meeting expectations for quality and accountability. In this context, institutional health checks—systematic assessments of leadership, governance, workplace culture, and organizational dynamics become especially important. These assessments help identify strengths and areas for improvement to foster a culture of quality and ensure long-term sustainability. They also provide evidence to inform ongoing strategic planning and quality assurance.

This study, therefore, aimed to synthesize the findings from the institutional evaluation into a coherent framework that not only diagnoses organizational conditions but also informs corrective actions such as training, policy revision, and mentorship. By

integrating thematic insights across the identified dimensions, the study offers a systematic baseline for continuous improvement. Moreover, it contributes to the literature on institutional quality assurance in Philippine higher education, highlighting how locally driven evaluations can serve both regulatory compliance and organizational development.

Research Objectives

1. Identify the leadership strengths that emerged from the institutional evaluation.
2. Examine the ethical concerns and negative workplace behaviors reported in the evaluation.
3. Analyze the improvement suggestions and reflections provided by stakeholders.
4. Synthesize findings across all dimensions to develop a corrective action framework that guides interventions in training, policy revision, and mentorship.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive qualitative research design to examine institutional conditions from the perspectives of personnel at a local higher education institution. Descriptive qualitative approaches are appropriate when the goal is to generate a comprehensive, data-driven account of a phenomenon without imposing preexisting theoretical frameworks. This design enabled the researchers to document leadership strengths, ethical concerns, negative workplace behaviors, and areas for improvement as they naturally emerged from stakeholder narratives. Qualitative approaches are particularly valuable in organizational studies because they enable exploration of workplace dynamics, relational patterns, and institutional practices that may not be captured by quantitative measures alone (Levitt, 2020). By grounding the inquiry into participants' experiences, the design supported a nuanced understanding of how leadership interactions and governance structures shape overall institutional health.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The participants comprised all faculty and administrative staff employed at the institution at the time of data collection. A census sampling technique was utilized to ensure full institutional representation. Census sampling is recommended for organizational assessments when the target population is manageable and diverse perspectives are necessary to avoid bias (Etikan & Babatope, 2019). This approach ensured that the dataset reflected diverse positions, hierarchical roles, and functional units, thereby enabling a richer, more comprehensive understanding of leadership interactions and organizational culture—a total of 232 personnel submitted valid responses. The census approach strengthened the credibility of findings by ensuring that the analysis was informed not by a subset of voices but by the collective perspectives of the entire institution.

Research Instrument

Data were collected using the Individual Leadership Evaluation Tool, an open-ended questionnaire designed to elicit narrative reflections on leadership effectiveness within the institution. The instrument included prompts asking participants to describe observed leadership strengths, ethical issues, negative workplace behaviors, suggested improvements, and general reflections. Open-ended tools are considered suitable in qualitative evaluations because they allow participants to share experiences in their own words, providing depth, context, and detail that structured tools may miss (Aspers & Corte, 2019). The tool's design also aligns with current leadership and governance research, which highlights the importance of capturing authentic, experience-based accounts to understand organizational health. The instrument's flexibility enabled stakeholders to provide detailed responses, thereby enriching the dataset.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection was part of an institutional health-check initiative led by the institution's Office of the President. Before distribution, staff were informed of the evaluation's purpose and voluntary nature. The questionnaire was shared with all employees via the institution's internal communication channels. Participants were given ample time to consider the questions and submit their narrative responses. This approach minimized disruption to work routines while enabling accurate and thoughtful input. All completed responses were compiled, anonymized, and organized for analysis. Following current best practices for qualitative data collection in organizational settings, clear instructions were provided to avoid confusion, and confidentiality was stressed to encourage honest feedback (Birt et al., 2016). Only responses from individuals who voluntarily participated were included in the final dataset.

Data Analysis Procedure

Data were analyzed using thematic analysis, following the enhanced six-phase framework developed by Braun and Clarke (2006). The process began by immersing oneself in the dataset through repeated readings to build familiarity with its content. This was followed by systematic initial coding, where meaningful sections of text were identified and labeled. Codes were then examined for similarities and grouped into preliminary themes. In the next step, themes were reviewed to ensure coherence, internal consistency, and distinctiveness. Themes were refined, labeled, and defined to accurately reflect their conceptual boundaries. Recent literature highlights that thematic analysis is particularly suitable for organizational research because of its flexibility and ability to reveal patterned meanings across qualitative datasets (Byrne, 2022). To increase analytic rigor, codes and themes were compared across responses from different organizational groups to ensure representation and prevent single-source bias. Finally, themes were organized into a Corrective Action Framework that connects diagnostic insights with actionable strategies in training, policy development, and mentorship.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Leadership strengths in the institutional evaluation

Table 1
Thematic Structure of Leadership Strengths Identified in the Institutional Evaluation

Selected Statements	Codes/Meaning Units	Subordinate Theme	Superordinate Theme
<i>“Very articulate in instructions with considerations.”</i>	Clear instructions; considerate communication	Clarity and empathy in communication	Effective Communication and Responsiveness
<i>“Keeps communication open and makes sure concerns are addressed right away.”</i>	Open communication and immediate response	Accessibility and responsiveness	
<i>“Communicate clearly and persuasively, listen actively, and provide constructive feedback.”</i>	Active listening; constructive feedback	Feedback-oriented communication	
<i>“Very easy to communicate with, kind, and passionate.”</i>	Warm interpersonal style; relational leadership	Interpersonal connectedness	
<i>“Her visions and goals are aligned to the mission and vision.”</i>	Mission alignment; strategic fit	Strategic alignment	Strategic and Visionary Leadership
<i>“Strategic thinking and able to plan ahead of time for the success of the institution.”</i>	Forward planning; anticipatory thinking	Proactive leadership	
<i>“Visionary thinkers setting long-term goals for the institution.”</i>	Long-term orientation; future direction	Vision setting	
<i>“Clear vision for where the institution is heading and works well with departments to make things happen.”</i>	Collaborative planning; unified direction	Vision-driven collaboration	
<i>“Guide team members in an excellent and comprehensive manner.”</i>	Guided autonomy; supportive delegation	Empowering leadership	Empowerment and Delegation

Selected Statements	Codes/Meaning Units	Subordinate Theme	Superordinate Theme
<i>“Empowers subordinates through guidance and training while promoting independence.”</i>	Autonomy; capability-building	Strength-based delegation	
<i>“Does not micromanage and shows trust in the team’s abilities.”</i>	Trust; autonomy	Non-micromanaging behavior	
<i>“Assigns tasks based on strengths instead of excessive supervision.”</i>	Strength-based assignment	Talent-focused delegation	
<i>“Upholds integrity and fairness in all engagements.”</i>	Integrity; fairness	Ethical leadership	Integrity and Professionalism
<i>“Very objective in work and demonstrates professionalism in everything.”</i>	Objectivity; consistent professionalism	Professional discipline	
<i>“Transparent leader and a good example, honest and respectful.”</i>	Transparency; respectful conduct	Role modeling	

Theme 1. Effective Communication and Responsiveness

Participants consistently emphasized leaders’ ability to communicate clearly, listen attentively, and address concerns promptly. One participant noted that a dean was *“very articulate in instructions with considerations,”* while another praised a VP who *“keeps communication open and makes sure concerns are addressed right away.”* Staff highlighted how leaders *“communicate clearly and persuasively, listen actively, and provide constructive feedback,”* with another noting that a director is *“very easy to communicate with, kind, and passionate.”* Both datasets converge in portraying communication as a core strength, though staff tended to emphasize interpersonal warmth, whereas leaders focused on clarity in problem-solving.

The convergence of these narratives reflects what contemporary leadership research has established: effective communication is a key predictor of trust, collaboration, and organizational climate (Newman et al., 2017). Staff tend to emphasize interpersonal warmth, aligning with findings that relational communication fosters psychological safety and team cohesion (Lee et al., 2020). Leaders, on the other hand, are often recognized for clarity and problem-solving communication, consistent with evidence that directive clarity supports role understanding and performance, especially in developing institutions.

Given these patterns, institutional improvements can be reinforced by formalizing communication channels such as regular town halls, structured feedback systems, and open forums for discussion. Therefore, strengthening both formal and informal communication mechanisms can build trust and promote smoother coordination as the institution continues to expand.

Theme 2. Strategic and Visionary Leadership

Leaders were often praised for aligning departmental goals with the overall institutional vision and planning for success. One respondent said, *“One of his strengths is that his visions and goals are aligned to the mission and vision,”* while another mentioned, *“Strategic thinking—he is able to plan ahead of time for the success of the institution.”* Staff described leaders as “visionary thinkers... setting long-term goals for the institution” and acknowledged one vice president for having a *“clear vision for where the institution is heading and working well with departments to make things happen.”*

Both datasets highlighted strategic thinking as a major strength, though faculty tended to associate it with mission-driven alignment, while staff focused on its operational value. This convergence aligns with contemporary leadership research, which shows that strategic alignment enhances institutional coherence, improves resource allocation, and boosts long-term stability (Nguyen et al., 2017). Visionary leadership is especially vital in higher education institutions experiencing growth, as it shapes organizational identity, programs, and culture during formative years.

Anticipatory leadership allows organizations to respond proactively to emerging demands, which is essential for institutions navigating rapid expansion or system-building. Vision-driven leaders, as staff describe, are better able to articulate long-term goals, foster cross-unit collaboration, and maintain momentum toward shared objectives (Cardno & Youngs, 2013).

In the context of a newly established local college, such leadership is invaluable. Visionary and strategic leaders help transform institutional aspirations into concrete actions and measurable outcomes, reducing fragmentation and creating shared direction. This convergence presents an opportunity to expand strategic and visionary leadership through succession-planning workshops, leadership retreats, and mentoring programs that develop future leaders capable of maintaining alignment with the institutional mission while effectively operationalizing institutional goals.

Theme 3. Empowerment and Delegation

Stakeholders often highlighted leaders’ ability to empower staff, delegate tasks, and foster independence. Participants described leaders who *“guide team members excellently and comprehensively”* and *“empower subordinates through proper guidance and training, while also promoting independence at work.”* Staff echoed this, noting that some heads *“do not micromanage and show trust in the team’s abilities”* and *“assign tasks based on strengths instead of excessive supervision.”*

There is strong convergence here: both datasets identify empowerment as a motivating factor and a trust-building element. There is some divergence in emphasis; leaders see empowerment as guidance, while staff view it as autonomy and independence. This pattern aligns with recent research on empowerment. Kim and Beehr (2021) discovered that empowerment works best when leaders combine support with autonomy, helping employees develop confidence, take initiative, and improve their skills.

Moreover, the staff's appreciation for non-micromanaging leadership aligns with research indicating that autonomy-supportive environments foster innovation, engagement, and intrinsic motivation. This is especially relevant in a newly established local college where human resources must quickly learn, adapt, and assume expanded roles as systems develop. To maintain this strength, leadership training can intentionally incorporate empowerment practices, and institutional policies can support distributed decision-making to amplify the benefits of delegated authority. Establishing formal structures that recognize empowered behavior both from leaders and staff can also formalize a culture of trust, autonomy, and shared responsibility.

Theme 4. Integrity and Professionalism

Professionalism, fairness, and integrity stand out as key strengths across the institution. Participants praised a vice president who *“upholds integrity and fairness in all engagements, setting a high standard of professionalism,”* and another who was described as *“very objective in work and demonstrates professionalism in everything.”* Staff highlighted leaders who are *“transparent leaders and good examples,”* noting their *“honesty and respect”* when interacting with subordinates.

Both datasets agree that integrity is crucial for trust. Integrity signals predictability in leaders' actions, which in turn enhances psychological safety and organizational unity (Avolio et al., 2020). The divergence lies mainly in emphasis: leaders are praised for fairness in their decisions, while staff focus on the daily demonstration of respectful behavior. This difference aligns with research on educational leadership, which shows that employees often judge integrity based on everyday interactions rather than on formal decisions alone (Nguyen et al., 2017). For many staff members, integrity is experienced not only when leaders make fair choices but also when they show respect, transparency, and humility in their interpersonal relationships.

In a newly established local college, integrity and professionalism become even more vital. Early on, institutions depend heavily on building trust to establish culture, align new processes, and reinforce shared values. When leaders consistently demonstrate respectful conduct and fairness, they set a moral foundation that influences employee expectations and the institution's identity. According to Lee et al. (2020), values-based leadership fosters a positive environment in which ethical standards are internalized rather than imposed.

This pattern emphasizes the need for institutional reinforcement of integrity through recognition systems, peer accountability mechanisms, and ethics-focused

leadership workshops. Such structures help ensure that integrity is embedded in organizational culture rather than practiced only by specific individuals. Institutions that formalize ethical expectations early are more likely to maintain fairness, transparency, and professionalism as they grow, expand, and diversify.

Ethical concerns and negative workplace behaviors emerged from the evaluation

Table 2. Thematic Structure

Selected Statements	Codes/Meaning Units	Subordinate Theme	Superordinate Theme
<i>“Fairness and honesty have been questioned, especially when choices are influenced by partiality, such as when processing refunds.”</i>	Perceived partiality; compromised fairness	Inconsistent accountability	Gaps in Accountability and Consistency
<i>“I heard about him endorsing his sibling and in-law... the hiring process was not transparent.”</i>	Nepotism concern; lack of transparency	Questionable hiring practices	
<i>“She frequently provides inconsistent information... while she takes credit for the accomplishments.”</i>	Inconsistent reporting; credit misattribution	Reliability and accountability issues	
<i>“She engages in direct communication with the President without consideration of proper communication channels.”</i>	Bypassing communication protocols	Procedural violations	Procedural Lapses and Reliability Issues
<i>“We discussed and agreed on certain matters, but later, she suddenly did not recall the agreement and claimed she never agreed to it.”</i>	Failure to honor agreements; unreliability	Agreement inconsistency	
<i>“Sometimes, she tends to make decisions on her own without consulting the team.”</i>	Unilateral decision-making; non-collaborative action	Lack of consultation	
<i>“There is a pressing need for professional development and ethical training among his staff, as their interactions with clients come across as dismissive or unwelcoming.”</i>	Poor client interaction; lack of professionalism	Staff development gaps	Gaps in Ethical Consistency and Staff Development

Selected Statements	Codes/Meaning Units	Subordinate Theme	Superordinate Theme
<i>“Financial processes lacked clear accountability structures, creating delays and perceptions of bias.”</i>	Weak accountability mechanisms; perceived bias	Ethical inconsistency in procedures	

Theme 1. Gaps in Accountability and Consistency

Participants highlighted situations where institutional processes and leadership practices did not consistently meet expected standards of accountability. One respondent noted that *“fairness and honesty have been questioned, especially when choices are influenced by partiality, such as when processing refunds.”* Others expressed concerns about hiring procedures, with one remarking, *“I heard about him endorsing his sibling and in-law... the hiring process was not transparent.”* Several participants also shared frustration over accomplishment reporting: *“She frequently provides inconsistent information... while she takes credit for the accomplishments.”* Overall, these accounts reveal gaps in how accountability and consistency are maintained, which can weaken trust and harm a culture of responsibility.

For a newly established local college, these issues are especially critical. If accountability norms are not clearly enforced early on, they risk becoming ingrained cultural patterns that persist as the institution grows. To prevent this, the college must strengthen transparent hiring practices, maintain consistent documentation, and establish mechanisms for fair decision-making. Improving these governance practices can help rebuild trust and foster a culture where fairness and responsibility are expected and consistently upheld.

Theme 2. Procedural Lapses and Reliability Issues

Some responses pointed to behaviors that blurred professional boundaries or raised questions about integrity. For example, one participant noted that *“she engages in direct communication with the president without consideration of the proper communication channels.”* Another mentioned an instance where *“we discussed and agreed on certain matters, but later, she suddenly did not recall the agreement and claimed she never agreed to it.”* Similarly, concerns were raised about leaders who bypassed collaborative decision-making, with one respondent observing, *“Sometimes, she tends to make decisions on her own without consulting the team.”* These behaviors highlight the importance of honoring agreements, respecting organizational protocols, and practicing transparent decision-making, as lapses in these areas may undermine trust and organizational cohesion.

Recent research supports these concerns. According to Hassan et al. (2014), leaders who bypass established protocols or fail to keep commitments undermine perceptions of reliability, a key aspect of ethical leadership. Additionally, inconsistent decision-making and the neglect of consultation undermine psychological safety and

discourage employees from openly contributing to organizational processes. For a newly formed local college, where structures and norms are still developing, such lapses can cause confusion, role ambiguity, and reduced collaboration. Improving communication protocols, documenting agreements, and promoting consultative decision-making can help restore consistency and ensure that everyday leadership actions match institutional expectations.

Theme 3. Gaps in Ethical Consistency and Staff Development

Several comments emphasized the need for stronger ethical modeling and staff development. One respondent noted that *“there is a pressing need for professional development and ethical training among his staff, as their interactions with clients often come across as dismissive or unwelcoming.”* Another mentioned that financial processes lacked clear accountability structures, leading to delays and perceptions of bias. These comments suggest that when leaders and their teams do not consistently demonstrate professionalism and courtesy, they risk normalizing incivility and inefficiency, which can reduce morale and lower service quality.

According to Ahmed et al. (2020), ethical modeling by leaders is crucial because employees tend to mirror the behavior they observe, which influences the organization's ethical climate. When ethical standards are inconsistently upheld, workplace incivility becomes more likely, resulting in lower morale and reduced service performance. Similarly, research by Park et al. (2018) found that inadequate training and unclear accountability structures contribute to inefficiencies and perceived unfairness in service-oriented environments. In a newly established local college, such gaps can significantly affect how clients, students, and partner agencies view the institution's reliability. Investing in ethics training, enhancing staff development programs, and formalizing accountability mechanisms can help ensure professionalism becomes a shared, consistently maintained organizational norm.

Negative Workplace Behaviors

Table 3. Thematic Structure for Negative Workplace Behaviors

Selected Statements	Codes/Meaning Units	Subordinate Theme	Superordinate Theme
<i>“She would publicly and loudly say negative things about her subordinates, leading the person to feel ashamed.”</i>	Public reprimand; harsh communication	Disrespectful communication	Respect and Professional Conduct in Interactions
<i>“Bad words to the Finance Dept.”</i>	Verbal disrespect; inappropriate language	Incivility in communication	

Selected Statements	Codes/Meaning Units	Subordinate Theme	Superordinate Theme
<i>“Her loudness... is a bit of an acquired taste.”</i>	Overbearing tone; sensitivity concerns	Communication tone issues	
<i>“She just logs in and goes elsewhere during the flag-raising.”</i>	Poor attendance; disengagement	Inconsistent presence	Weak Work Discipline and Presence
<i>“He has been out of the school lately... it has been frequent.”</i>	Absenteeism; lack of visibility	Weak work discipline	
<i>“There have been occasional concerns regarding his attendance.”</i>	Unreliable presence	Attendance inconsistency	
<i>“Some tasks are imposed on team members even though they are not part of their job.”</i>	Role misalignment; overload	Misassigned responsibilities	Misalignment of Tasks and Reporting
<i>“Too many irrelevant tasks could cause burnout and disengagement.”</i>	Role strain; risk of burnout	Work overload	
<i>“The leader tends to provide vague descriptions of accomplishments... with limited documentation.”</i>	Poor reporting; lack of evidence	Inadequate accomplishment reporting	
<i>“Attitude, sometimes unpredictable.”</i>	Emotional unpredictability	Temperament concerns	Temperament and Sensitivity Issues
<i>“Rarely, he has a temper that may influence the atmosphere inside the office.”</i>	Emotional volatility; negative influence	Sensitivity issues	
<i>“Straightforward... but at times comes across as lacking sensitivity, provoking emotional reactions.”</i>	Blunt communication; low emotional intelligence	Lack of interpersonal sensitivity	
<i>“Focusing too much on minor details could cause delay in addressing bigger issues.”</i>	Overcontrol; misplaced priorities	Inefficient work focus	Isolated Negative Behaviors Affecting Workplace Dynamics

Selected Statements	Codes/Meaning Units	Subordinate Theme	Superordinate Theme
<i>“Decisions previously agreed upon were later denied or forgotten.”</i>	Unreliable decision-making; inconsistency	Procedural unreliability	
<i>“His impartiality and tendency to grant favors only when he is directly involved create an unfair workplace dynamic.”</i>	Favoritism; partiality	Perceived unfairness	
<i>“Concentrating on selected programs at the expense of others.”</i>	Imbalance in priorities	Uneven program support	
<i>“Sometimes blunt or inclined to rationalize staff shortcomings rather than address them directly.”</i>	Avoidance of accountability; bluntness	Ineffective management style	

Theme 1. Respect and Professional Conduct in Interactions

Several participants expressed concerns about how some leaders interacted with staff. They described instances where leaders spoke harshly or embarrassed subordinates in public: *“She would publicly and loudly say things negatively about her subordinates, leading the person to feel ashamed.”* Another respondent simply said, *“bad words to a certain Dept.”* Others noted that a leader’s *“loudness... is a bit of an acquired taste.”* These accounts show that while leaders might effectively communicate their messages, lapses in tone, courtesy, and sensitivity can foster resentment, decrease psychological safety, and hinder open collaboration.

In new institutions like local colleges, where organizational norms are still developing, these instances of incivility can quickly become cultural patterns that discourage honest dialogue and lower employee engagement. Addressing these behaviors early with coaching, professional conduct guidelines, and communication training is crucial to prevent long-term relational issues and to cultivate a respectful and supportive institutional culture.

Theme 2. Weak Work Discipline and Presence

Participants also raised concerns about leaders’ attendance and engagement. One described that *“she just logs in and goes elsewhere during the flag-raising,”* while another reported, *“I have observed that he’s been out of the school lately... it has been frequent.”* Even occasional lapses were noted: *“There have been occasional concerns regarding his attendance.”* When leaders show inconsistent presence, they risk signaling disengagement, which can decrease team motivation and effectiveness.

Research shows that visible and consistent leadership presence boosts employee morale, encourages accountability, and enhances organizational commitment (Dirani et al., 2020). In a developing local college where staff look to leaders for guidance, demonstrating discipline is especially important. Irregular attendance by leaders can unintentionally suggest that institutional routines are unimportant, thereby influencing staff behavior. Implementing clear accountability systems and increasing leadership visibility can help prevent disengagement and strengthen the collective work ethic.

Theme 3. Misalignment of Tasks and Reporting

Several participants raised concerns about the alignment between responsibilities and outputs. One respondent said, *“some tasks are imposed on team members even though they are not part of their job... Too many irrelevant tasks could cause burnout and disengagement.”* Another criticized the accomplishment reporting, noting that *“the leader tends to provide vague descriptions of accomplishments in her report, with limited to no supporting documentation.”* These comments indicate gaps in aligning tasks with staff roles and clearly presenting achievements. When responsibilities and reports do not align with organizational expectations, staff may feel overburdened, disengaged, or skeptical of the accuracy of performance evaluations.

Studies show that role clarity and accurate reporting are crucial for employee satisfaction and organizational efficiency (Park et al., 2018). When tasks are mismatched with staff skills or job descriptions, burnout and disengagement become more likely. Likewise, unclear achievement reporting decreases transparency and damages trust in leadership. For a newly established local college, improving job descriptions, standardizing documentation formats, and adopting monitoring tools would help ensure fairness, streamline workflow, and boost credibility in performance evaluations.

Theme 4. Temperament and Sensitivity Issues

Finally, issues of temperament and interpersonal sensitivity were observed. One respondent simply stated, *“attitude, sometimes unpredictable.”* Another noted that *“rarely, he has a temper that may influence the atmosphere inside the office.”* Similarly, a leader’s communication style was described as *“straightforward... but at times comes across as lacking sensitivity, provoking emotional reactions.”* These accounts suggest that unmanaged temperament and bluntness can create a tense environment, reducing psychological safety and collaboration.

Emotional instability and insensitive communication styles have been linked to decreased teamwork, increased stress, and impaired decision-making in organizations (Kaluza et al., 2020). During the early stages of a local college’s development, leaders’ emotional tone greatly influences the workplace atmosphere and employee expectations. When leaders exhibit unpredictable or blunt behavior, employees may be reluctant to voice concerns or share ideas, which limits innovation and collaborative problem-solving. Providing emotional intelligence training and reflective supervision can help leaders manage interpersonal dynamics more effectively.

Theme 5. Isolated Negative Behaviors Affecting Workplace Dynamics

Although many participants reported no concerns, several highlighted specific negative behaviors affecting the workplace. One leader was described as focusing excessively on minor details, which “could cause delay in addressing bigger issues.” Another issue involved inconsistency in agreements, with “decisions previously agreed upon were later denied or forgotten.” Favoritism was also noted, with one remarking that “his impartiality and tendency to grant favors only when he is directly involved create an unfair workplace dynamic.” In some cases, participants pointed to an imbalance in priorities, such as focusing on certain programs at the expense of others. Lastly, issues of temperament and accountability were raised, with leaders described as sometimes blunt or inclined to rationalize staff shortcomings rather than address them directly. These behaviors, while not widespread, demonstrate how lapses in fairness, reliability, or management style can undermine trust, efficiency, and morale.

In the context of a developing local college, these behaviors may also derail emerging systems and skew work priorities. Addressing them through clear communication protocols, documented agreements, and accountability mechanisms will help prevent these isolated issues from becoming entrenched organizational patterns.

Improvement suggestions and reflections by stakeholders

Table 4: Leader and system-level feedback, core insights, and themes

Dataset A (Leader-Specific Feedback)	Dataset B (System-Level Feedback)	Core Insight	Theme
<i>“Put fairness and impartiality first.”</i>	<i>“Minutes and note-taking should be implemented; task delegation must be clear.”</i>	Clear, inclusive communication requires both fairness and structured documentation.	Communication & Decision-Making
<i>“Improve consistency and follow-through; strengthen accountability.”</i>	<i>“Enhance strategic and fiscal management; issue formal memorandums.”</i>	Leadership capacity improves when personal accountability aligns with institutional policy systems.	Leadership Accountability
<i>“Balance constructive criticism with positive reinforcement.”</i>	<i>“Strengthen personnel connection beyond administrative tasks.”</i>	Collaboration thrives when feedback is constructive and workplace relationships are nurtured.	Team Collaboration
<i>“Plan ahead so staff have time to comply with requirements.”</i>	<i>“Implement a tracking system and assign a point person.”</i>	Planning and efficiency improve when strategic	Systems Efficiency

Dataset A (Leader-Specific Feedback)	Dataset B (System-Level Feedback)	Core Insight	Theme
<i>“Motivate staff for growth and development.”</i>	<i>“Promote continuous learning and encourage learning from mistakes.”</i>	leadership is supported by monitoring tools. Professional growth is maximized when leader-driven motivation aligns with an institutional learning culture.	Continuous Learning
<i>“Maintain a wise, kind, and giving character.”</i>	<i>“Continue good deeds for the community.”</i>	Positive leadership traits strengthen institutional morale and must be preserved alongside reforms.	Positive Leadership Traits

Theme 1. Communication and Decision-Making

Stakeholders described communication and decision-making as vital areas that need improvement to support institutional coherence. Feedback repeatedly highlighted the need for clearer, fairer, and better-recorded communication practices. Participants noted that decisions should be based on impartiality, while system-level comments emphasized documenting meetings, clarifying delegation, and ensuring timely information sharing. These insights show that communication gaps stem not only from personal habits but also from the lack of structured communication systems. In a newly established local college, where policies and workflows are still developing, strengthening communication protocols is a key step for building trust and avoiding misunderstandings.

Theme 2. Leadership Accountability

Leadership accountability became a key theme, with respondents stressing the importance of consistency, follow-through, and clear communication of directives. Feedback specific to leaders identified gaps in decision-making consistency, while comments at the system level emphasized the need for clearer policies, formal memorandums, and compliance with agreed processes. These assessments indicate that accountability must operate on two levels: individual responsibility and organizational structure. For a young local college navigating growth, misalignment between leader behavior and institutional policies can easily undermine operational flow and trust.

Theme 3. Team Collaboration

Team collaboration was another recurring theme, with participants emphasizing the importance of balanced feedback, interpersonal connection, and opportunities for positive social interaction. Leader-focused comments highlighted the need to balance constructive criticism with encouragement, while office-level feedback stressed the value

of building camaraderie beyond task-related interactions. This dynamic illustrates the dual nature of workplace collaboration, which depends on both leaders' relational behaviors and the organization's cultural norms. Research supports this, noting that workplaces grounded in supportive relationships and balanced feedback practices experience higher morale, stronger engagement, and greater overall cohesion (Camps et al., 2016). These insights are especially relevant for institutions still shaping their identity, values, and internal culture.

Theme 4. Systems Efficiency

System efficiency became a priority, with respondents highlighting gaps in planning, time management, and process monitoring. Leader-specific comments called for more proactive planning aligned with institutional goals, while system-level feedback stressed the need for tracking mechanisms and designated focal persons to oversee workflow. For a growing college with expanding functions, operational inefficiencies can increase and delay task completion. The literature supports the importance of organized processes in educational environments, with findings indicating that structured workflow systems improve task clarity, reduce bottlenecks, and enhance organizational responsiveness (Avolio et al., 2009). Therefore, strengthening both leadership planning and technical systems is essential for enhancing institutional performance.

Theme 5. Professional Growth and Continuous Learning

Professional growth and continuous learning were emphasized as key parts of institutional development. Respondents expressed a desire for greater motivation to learn, more organized mentorship opportunities, and an institutional culture that normalizes learning from mistakes. Leader-specific insights highlighted the need for personalized support, while system-level comments focused on creating a reflective, learning-focused environment. Studies confirm the importance of such cultures, noting that when educational institutions promote continuous learning, they encourage adaptability, innovation, and long-term resilience (Carmeli, 2010). For a newly established college, integrating continuous learning practices helps staff adapt to changing roles and boosts organizational capacity.

Theme 6. Positive Leadership Traits

Positive leadership traits were widely acknowledged as stabilizing forces within the institution. Participants consistently appreciated leaders who showed kindness, humility, and a dedication to service. These behaviors appeared to significantly affect morale, particularly during periods of organizational change. In a young institution with developing systems, positive relational leadership can help manage growing pains and foster a culture of trust and respect. Contemporary leadership studies support this, showing that leaders who demonstrate compassion and humility improve employees' sense of belonging and psychological safety (Hoch, 2018). Such traits not only enhance interpersonal relationships but also support the college's emerging identity as a values-driven organization.

INTEGRATED INSTITUTIONAL IMPROVEMENT FRAMEWORK

The framework combines the three major domains identified in the study: (1) **Leadership Strengths**; (2) **Ethical and Behavioral Gaps**; and (3) **Improvement Pathways**. It integrates these into a **four-pillar system**, aligned with **PDCA**, **PAASCU quality areas**, and the unique developmental context of a newly established local college.

Table 5
Integrated Framework: Four Pillars of Institutional Health

Pillar	Key Findings from Institutional Data	Implication	PDCA Focus	PAASCU Alignment
1. Leadership Capacity & Character	Strong communication, integrity, empowerment, humility, relational warmth	Leverage strengths to shape culture and anchor reforms.	Plan & Do	Leadership & Governance
2. Ethical & Behavioral Consistency	Issues of partiality, unprofessional conduct, protocol bypassing, attendance gaps	Ethical risks weaken trust and must be corrected systematically.	Check & Act	Leadership, QA, HR Policy
3. Systems & Operational Strengthening	Need for documentation, tracking tools, and planning systems	Improve efficiency through standardized processes.	Plan & Check	Quality Assurance, Support Services
4. Learning, Collaboration & Culture Building	Calls for teamwork, continuous learning, and professional development	Culture must evolve to support innovation and resilience.	Do & Act	HR Policy, Teaching-Learning, Institutional Culture

Table 5 presents an integrated framework that organizes the findings into four interconnected pillars of institutional health, illustrating how leadership behaviors, ethical practices, systems, and culture interact to shape the development of a new local college. The first pillar, Leadership Capacity and Character, reflects the institution's strong foundation. Stakeholders consistently described leaders as clear communicators, fair, empowering, humble, and relationally warm. These qualities are genuine; they actively influence how people experience work, how trust is built, and how change is accepted. Consequently, this pillar suggests that the college can strategically leverage its leadership strengths to influence organizational culture and serve as an anchor for reforms. Within the PDCA cycle, this mainly occurs in the Plan and Do phases, where leaders set direction, communicate expectations, and embody the values the institution aims to institutionalize. In terms of PAASCU alignment, these strengths are most evident in

Leadership and Governance, where strong leadership character supports legitimacy and coherence at the top.

The second pillar, Ethical and Behavioral Consistency, complements the first pillar's strengths by highlighting the risks that arise when behavior fails to align with institutional expectations. The data showed concerns about bias in decisions, unprofessional language, bypassing proper channels, and inconsistent attendance. Even when these behaviors involve only some leaders or occur occasionally, their impact on trust and morale is significant, especially in a young organization. This pillar emphasizes that ethical risks need to be addressed systematically rather than as isolated interpersonal issues. They undermine confidence in leadership, threaten workplace fairness, and cause confusion among staff regarding standards. In PDCA terms, this pillar primarily falls within the Check and Act phases. The institution must monitor ethical and behavioral patterns through climate surveys, feedback mechanisms, and HR reports, then take action with corrective coaching, policy improvements, and clear consequences. PAASCU areas related to leadership, quality assurance, and human resource policy are involved here, as they all require evidence that institutional decisions and behaviors are fair, transparent, and professionally sound.

The third pillar, Systems and Operational Strengthening, shifts the focus from people to processes. Stakeholders highlighted the need for more dependable documentation, tracking tools, and planning systems. These comments demonstrate that even with good intentions and capable leaders, work can still become inefficient or confusing without clear procedures or monitoring tools. At a newly established local college, many processes are still developing, so the risks of missed deadlines, lost requests, and overlapping tasks are higher. Therefore, this pillar emphasizes that efficiency and clarity depend not only on personal discipline but also on system design. Within the PDCA cycle, this pillar is vital to the Plan and Check stages, as well-designed processes support planning and tracking tools and records enable monitoring. This closely aligns with PAASCU's concerns regarding quality assurance and support services, in which documentation, system responsiveness, and institutional reliability are key indicators of maturity.

The fourth pillar, Learning, Collaboration, and Culture Building, highlights the relational and developmental aspects of the findings. Participants not only asked for rules and systems; they also called for stronger teamwork, more intentional opportunities for professional growth, and a culture that views mistakes as learning opportunities rather than failures. This reflects stakeholders' understanding that institutional health goes beyond compliance to encompass growth, innovation, and shared responsibility. In a young college, this pillar is vital for transforming the institution from a collection of structures into a true community. Within PDCA, this pillar is most active in the Do and Act phases, where programs are executed, feedback is used for improvement, and learning becomes part of daily practice. It aligns with PAASCU domains related to human resource policy, teaching and learning, and Institutional Culture, all of which emphasize development, collaboration, and a supportive environment.

Taken together, the four pillars in Table 5 illustrate that institutional health in a new local college is not a single dimension but a dynamic interplay of leadership character, ethical consistency, process reliability, and learning culture. Leadership strengths lay the foundation; ethical and behavioral consistency maintains trust; systems strengthening ensures work is done efficiently and fairly; and a culture of learning and collaboration helps the institution adapt and grow. This integrated framework shows that reforms should not be piecemeal. Instead, they should intentionally connect people, processes, and culture, guided by PDCA logic and aligned with PAASCU standards, to support a coherent and sustainable path toward institutional maturity.

Conclusions

The institutional health check revealed that the college is at a crucial developmental point where strong leadership qualities coexist with emerging organizational challenges that must be addressed to ensure long-term success. The evaluation highlighted notable leadership strengths, particularly clarity of communication, integrity, empowerment practices, and relational warmth, that have helped stabilize the institution and build trust during its early stages. These strengths serve as cultural anchors that can be strategically used to guide organizational reforms. At the same time, the study identified ethical and behavioral inconsistencies that weaken these strengths, including partiality in decision-making, bypassing protocols, inconsistent attendance, and unprofessional interactions. Such gaps emphasize the need for clearer standards of conduct, stronger accountability measures, and consistent modeling of ethical leadership across all levels of administration.

Beyond leadership behaviors, the findings highlight significant system-level needs, especially in documentation, planning, task delegation, monitoring, and process standardization. These operational gaps reduce efficiency and cause inconsistencies that can hinder organizational performance, particularly in a rapidly growing institution. Stakeholders' suggestions further stress the importance of fostering a culture of teamwork, ongoing learning, and professional development, understanding that institutional growth requires not just strong systems but also stronger relationships, shared responsibility, and reflective practice.

The four-pillar framework—Leadership Capacity and Character, Ethical and Behavioral Consistency, Systems and Operational Strengthening, and Learning, Collaboration, and Culture Building—offers a clear roadmap for institutional improvement. When aligned with the PDCA cycle and PAASCU quality areas, it shows that sustainable reform requires integrating people-centered leadership development, ethical governance, efficient systems, and a culture that promotes both accountability and innovation. Ultimately, the study concludes that the institution has the core strengths needed to move toward organizational maturity, but these strengths must be systematically reinforced through deliberate policy development, capacity building, and culture-shaping efforts. By focusing on these interconnected areas, the college can move from basic stability to lasting excellence and become a more resilient, responsive, and values-driven higher education institution.

Recommendations

1. Strengthen institutional governance by formalizing ethical and accountability mechanisms that promote fairness, transparency, and consistency in decision-making. Clear policies and documented procedures should be enforced to address partiality, procedural lapses, and gaps in accountability across all levels of the institution.
2. Improve leadership skills through ongoing professional development focused on ethical practices, emotional intelligence, communication abilities, and values-driven decision-making. Organized mentoring and coaching programs can assist leaders in demonstrating professionalism and building trust within the organization.
3. Standardize systems and operational processes by establishing clear guidelines for task delegation, documentation, monitoring, and reporting. Streamlined procedures will improve efficiency, reduce role ambiguity, and ensure consistency in institutional operations.
4. Foster a collaborative and psychologically safe work environment by encouraging open communication, inclusive dialogue, and constructive feedback mechanisms. Promoting participation and mutual respect will help build trust, strengthen teamwork, and support collective problem-solving.
5. Institutionalize ongoing learning and performance improvement through regular training, reflective practices, and mentoring programs. Consistent investment in human capital will strengthen ethical behavior, boost competence, and support long-term organizational growth.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical research standards by ensuring voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality of responses, and responsible data management. All procedures-maintained principles of integrity, respect, and accountability to protect participants and uphold the research's credibility. AI tools were used solely for language editing, with minimal impact on the substantive content.

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